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Gender-based violence and its prevention in university nursing areas

Guillermina Arenas-Montaña ^{1,*}, Elizabeth Alejandrina Guzmán Hernández ², Ariel Ramírez-Cortes ¹, Elmy Alonzo Rodríguez ³, María de los Ángeles Torres Lagunas ⁴ and Elsy Guadalupe Vega Morales ⁵

¹ National Autonomous University of Mexico, Faculty of Higher Education Iztacala, Tlanepantla, State of Mexico, 54090, Mexico.

² Medical Surgeon Career, Faculty of Higher Studies Iztacala, National Autonomous University of Mexico, Tlanepantla, State of Mexico, 54090, Mexico.

³ Autonomous University of Yucatan, Merida, Mexico

⁴ Nursing and Obstetrics Career, Division of Professional Studies ENEO-UNAM. Mexico City, Mexico.

⁵ Yucatan Health Services, Siglo XXI Temporary Care Center, State Nursing Coordination, Merida Yucatan, Mexico.

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Abstract

Gender violence is a public health problem that occurs in all areas of society, especially affecting women. In university spaces, various types of violence are experienced in which force and the exercise of power are used to cause harm to the victims. The consequences that occur are of varying magnitude, including emotional and psychological disturbances, poor academic performance, school dropouts, suicide, and social conflicts. Analyzing and identifying the practices of gender violence in university spaces will allow us to propose strategies to recognize it, prevent it, report it and eradicate it.

Keywords: Violence; Gender Violence: School Violence: Power and Gender relations;

1. Introduction

The objective of this review is to describe some elements that provoke gender violence among young university students, among them, power relations, gender inequalities between women and men, and how these extend to public workspaces. Likewise, some proposals that educational institutions formulate to prevent, address and eradicate gender violence within university environments are exposed. The purpose of this manuscript is to reflect on gender violence and its prevention in university spaces to propose strategies for maintaining a more just, egalitarian, harmonious, healthy university environment so that students can recognize, denounce and prevent violence.

2. Gender violence in university spaces, elements that provoke it

The study of gender violence is relevant, especially in universities, since these institutions have a fundamental role in the formation and dissemination of ideologies. Within which are the rules that subordinate the feminine to the masculine, which represents structural violence where men are located in a superior position, thereby maintaining the asymmetries of power and gender violence [1].

In educational institutions, efforts have been made to help prevent and eradicate gender violence in these spaces. Among these, we can mention the violent meter, designed at the National Polytechnic Institute, and the strategies

* Corresponding author: Guillermina Arenas-Montaña

National Autonomous University of Mexico, Faculty of Higher Education Iztacala, Tlanepantla, State of Mexico, 54090, Mexico.

proposed by the University Program for Gender Studies (PUEG) of the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM).

Regarding research related to gender violence focused on university students (men and women), the international study on partner violence (International Dating Violence Study) stands out, in which university students from 32 nations were surveyed. In the data obtained in this study, high percentages of physical violence in the couple were observed [2].

The UNAM is part of the higher education system, a public regime institution, training professionals, where disciplinary and scientific knowledge is built and innovated, the social inclusion of students from different social and generational sectors is favored and contributes to the training and strengthening of values and behaviors. Likewise, it has the social responsibility of organizing equitable environments that favor equal academic, work, and professional opportunities for its student, teaching, and administrative community. However, although the presence of women in this educational space has increased throughout its history in all its sectors, such incorporation in many cases is conditioned by gender inequality that hinders access, permanence, and social mobility of women [3].

It must be recognized that one of the main peculiarities of our cultures and intellectual traditions is that they focus on the paradigm of the interests and experiences of man, who is perceived as a paradigm of the human being; then the institutions created socially, respond mainly to the needs and interests of the man and at most to the needs and interests that he believes that women have, consequently, by not considering the experiences of women, the result is their invisibility and violations of their human rights [1].

Both men and women suffer and resist circumstances of gender violence, but the risk factors, types, and effects of violence are not the same for women as for men. We can define gender violence as "That type of violence that one sex exerts on the other; that is, the violent action of a man to a woman, or vice versa" [2]. It can also be defined as "The exercise of violence that reflects the existing asymmetry in power relations between men and women, and that perpetuates the subordination and devaluation of the feminine against the masculine." The Health Sciences descriptor defines it as the result of physical, sexual, or psychological harm, including threats, coercion, or deprivation of liberty, occurring in public and private life (DeCS). Gender-based violence is a public health and human rights problem throughout the world, the modality, prevalence, and incidence of this type of violence vary depending on the place. It is evident that, although human rights violations affect both men and women, their impact and character vary according to the sex of the victim [3-4].

Gender violence is a type of violence that occurs from giving less value to what is feminine (or what can be feminized) compared to what is masculine. It reproduces itself through history through cultural habits; The main victims of this violence are women, but also disadvantaged people, for example, boys and girls, the elderly, and human beings of different sexual orientations such as transsexuals, and homosexuals [5].

To understand the violence that is generated within the university, it is important to know the framework of institutional culture, through its daily practices in which power relations, stereotypes, representations, norms, and social values are articulated, [5] is mentioned the existence of factors that guide the analysis of the origin of violent acts within higher education institutions, among which are individual factors: violent acts or submission, the crisis of values, struggle for power, addictions, and individualism [6] and the interpersonal factors that derive from the lack of communication, rivalry, competition, and family breakdown, which in turn lead to the growing scarcity of values, the transgression of norms within university spaces and reinforce gender violence.

According to the General Law on Women's Access to a Life Free of Violence, several types of violence are identified: psychological (any act or omission that damages psychological stability); physical (any act that inflicts non-accidental harm, using physical force or some type of weapon or object); the patrimonial (any act or omission that affects the survival of the victim); economic violence (any action or omission of the aggressor that affects the economic survival of the victim"); and sexual violence (any act that degrades or damages the body and/or sexuality of the victim and therefore violates her freedom, dignity, and physical integrity). In the case of sexual violence, a distinction must be made between sexual harassment (which occurs in a horizontal relationship, where there is no subordinate relationship) and sexual harassment (when the violence occurs in a hierarchical relationship and, therefore, there is a component of domination/subordination) [7].

Among the different forms of violence, it is worth highlighting that which comes from the relationships established in the teaching and labor spheres, derived from the combination of hierarchical and horizontal relationships. In educational spaces, these two types of violence converge, since there are labor relations between those who work in the

institution, at the same time as there is the interaction between teachers and students, and between the students themselves. This favors an environment prone to gender violence [8].

The recognition of gender violence is fundamental, to prevent, address and eradicate it, however, among the students there is difficulty in identifying, knowing, and accepting the behaviors that are part of gender violence, which causes them to go unnoticed, become everyday and accepted as normal behaviors [9].

In most cases, gender-based violence experienced by students is correlated with lower academic performance and school dropout. For example, in the United States, it is estimated that 1 in 5 university students are survivors of attempted rape or rape. completed rape, 5% of them report having been victimized. In Switzerland, 18.6% of adolescent women enrolled in schools reported an experience of sexual victimization, while in India, 33% of adolescent girls of school age had experienced some form of sexual abuse, Latin America is located as the second deadliest region for women, with a rate of 1.6 per 100,000 inhabitants, in Mexico according to the National Survey on the Dynamics of Relationships in Households (ENDIREH) 2016, indicates that in the last 12 months 25% of the women who have attended the school have experienced any type of gender-based violence and of the aggressions that occurred in said space it was sexual [9]. About the aggressor, the partner is reported in 39.9%, partner 20.1%, male teacher 14.4%, female teacher 5%, administrative staff 2.1%, and directors 1.1%. A study conducted at the FES Iztacala UNAM showed that, About psychological violence, it reflected that control behavior, compared to blackmail, is more present in the student body and that women identify it more frequently than men [10].

Gender-based violence in universities is a frequent but little recognized fact, the lack of a culture of denunciation by those who are or have been victims of these situations, do not know where or with whom to go to denounce. Most of the students who suffer from gender violence are women and only some of them denounce it since there is a tendency to minimize the abuse considering that it is something unimportant, they are afraid, they lack information, there is mistrust in the authorities, they do not want their families to find out or because of shame; In addition, in many cases, there is a tendency to blame the victim and it is even accepted that violence is part of conflict resolution, which leads to the problem being minimized and the fault of the abuser being ignored [11]. Likewise, the subject is so little known that authorities and academic faculty do not give importance to the problem due to a lack of interest and inexperience in how to proceed in these cases, or because they are considered to be personal problems, a situation that it can favor the reproduction of gender violence inside and outside educational institutions.

3. Power and gender relations

In higher education institutions, power relations and inequalities are reproduced between women and men related to the profession that is practiced and the violence that arises extends from educational spaces to work. The reasoning is based on gender inequalities, which are based on a sexual division of labor, which assigns women the primary responsibility for unpaid domestic work and care for dependents, especially girls, boys, the disabled, the elderly, and the sick From which derive a series of disadvantages experienced by women about men, which affect both their academic, work and private life, thus inequality means that women are considered inferior and subordinate to men [12].

Gender inequalities are a social phenomenon that is symbolically sustained by relationships of value and power between the feminine and the masculine [13]. The historical and current feminist struggle has strengthened women's access to various levels of education and with it their participation in the labor market, which is increasing more and more, however, their presence is predominant in the tertiary sector. The activities of commerce and services represent the activity where the highest percentage of the employed female population is inserted, 25.8% and 53.2%, respectively [14].

There is also evidence related to educational spaces and employment, where certain professions are restricted to men or women, justified by biological differences and the division of labor imposed according to gender roles, thus promoting occupational segregation for reasons of gender. In the health sciences, the presence of women is concentrated in the Nursing profession, a discipline in which the traditional roles of women who care for other people at different stages of life continue to be perpetuated, assigning priority to states of suffering and alterations of health. However, this activity related to life and health care, necessary for human development, is culturally associated with the feminine from a patriarchal culture and therefore with a lower social and economic value [14].

In this regard, it can be said that nurses remain in positions and spaces socially reserved for them, where the practices they must develop have been designed and categorically implemented, and that many times they become exhausting routines inside hospitals, a situation that prevents them from progressing in their professional careers on the same terms as male nurses and other disciplines. It is argued that in the process of educational formation of the subjects there

is a hidden curriculum that directs them and is related to the discourses, practices, ideology, norms, policies, and institutions, which build the process of subjectivity through the relationship with others. In this way, the body is discovered as an object and target of power, a docile, subdued body that obeys, is educated, becomes skillful, and can be transformed and perfected through methods that allow detailed control of the body's operations, and that guarantees the constant subjection of its forces, imposing a relationship of docility-utility, that is, disciplining it to be both a productive body and a subjugated body [15].

The purpose is achieved not only by using violence and ideology but other forces can also be used, such as acting on material elements, however, as everything happens in a reflexive and organized way, subtle and refined violence is also produced that goes unnoticed and appears an order [15]. Institutions such as schools and hospitals participate in the construction of their social agents, through the reproduction and strengthening of gender stereotypes, culturally imposed on men and women, with asymmetric distributions of power and with a tendency toward a privileged hegemonic position for men. Thus producing gender inequalities and violence, which are naturalized or normalized and are not identified as practices of violence. The discipline imposed by the hierarchies of power and gender stereotypes poured into the hidden curriculum produces submissive and docile bodies, to increase their vigor and the production process [15]. Therefore, naturalizing violence refers to the process of accustoming and entrenching those actions where force and intimidation are used in their various forms of expression to achieve a purpose, which allows violence to gain ground in the culture. And it spreads stealthily, in such a way that nobody protests and it is justified [16]. This is how in the school space, a space of coexistence and generation of knowledge, different power relations are also reproduced and, consequently, naturalized, institutionalized, and accepted violence by the community [17].

Likewise, the division of labor and the labor market is not neutral, it remains organized from social and power spaces, where it is intended to preserve gender gaps in terms of the type of employment, social and economic recognition, and exclusion from leadership positions. And possibilities of social mobility. In this way, two basic forms of segregation in the labor market are strengthened: one is horizontal segregation, which is rooted in the unequal distribution of women and men in the different sectors of the economy or various occupations, and the vertical segregation is represented by unequal participation of women and men at different levels of the occupational hierarchy. Both segregations ultimately produce structures of domination and subordination between men and women [18].

The processes and relationships that form and sustain the division of labor are developed in chosen spaces, which are used to give them shape and specific characteristics. It is about relationships and socio-spatial processes in various contexts such as housing, hospital, institutes, and school among others [19]. This is how the subjects submit to the domain and dependence of another, that is, as a result of power, order, and command of someone, moving through a form of power that oppresses and constitutes the subject [20].

Gender-based violence in schools and hospitals affects the physical, psychological, and social health of students, their participation, and academic performance, and encourages school dropout. There is evidence that, within the university context, a series of prejudices are maintained that are inserted into the dynamics of everyday life. Studies carried out through interviews, questionnaires and focus groups reveal cultures that are adverse to women, in which contempt, denigration and repeated situations of bullying and harassment prevail, as well as the reactions and responses to these events within the institutions that reflect gender inequalities and gender violence that could be eradicated through a culture of education for peace [20].

Within institutions, talking about gender violence becomes more complex due to the various factors that are involved, since violence within these places affects managers, students, parents, etc. [21] Likewise, classrooms mean more than just impart or educate. Well, here various questions are raised for the personnel of the institutions in charge of promoting respect and education that they will impart to the citizens of today and tomorrow.

What kind of citizens do we imagine to build an adequate society? These types of questions help plan the objectives and the measures that will be taken so that the students who are the future of society have adequate preparation and information for respect among the same society that seeks to reduce the number of events in the country [21]. Although there are a variety of actions aimed at preventing violence and providing care and support to victims, in general, these are carried out without coordination, with limited resources, and with different orientations. There are also no diagnoses related to violence, which prevents starting from a basis for policy planning.

What to do to prevent address and eradicate gender violence in university spaces?

By international and national legislation, the Rectors of the Network of Macro-universities of Latin America and the Caribbean, together with the National Autonomous University of Mexico, commit to prevent and combat violence

through legal reforms normative and academic to achieve an egalitarian, inclusive, fair, open and committed transformation by following and strengthening its established lines of action [18].

However, despite the existence of this regulation, only some public, and private universities have a protocol or guidelines to address and solve the problem of violence against women in universities. Each of them is listed below [19].

- Regulation for the prevention, care, and punishment of harassment and sexual harassment at the Autonomous University of Sinaloa (2012).
- Guide for dealing with cases of harassment and sexual harassment of the Universidad Veracruzana (2013).
- Protocol for handling cases of gender violence at the National Autonomous University of Mexico. Second version. (2019).
- Protocol for attention to cases of gender violence of the University of Guanajuato (2019).
- Protocol for the prevention, action, and eradication of gender violence at the Universidad Michoacan de San Nicolás de Hidalgo (2017).
- Protocol of El Colegio de México to prevent acts of gender violence and to deal with cases of sexual harassment and sexual harassment (2019).

Among the private universities that have a protocol for the eradication of gender violence are the Ibero-American University with a (Gender Violence Attention Committee), the Action Committee against Gender Violence for the Technologic de Monterrey, and the Institutional Committee against Sexual Harassment for ITAM) they specify how the people who will integrate it will be selected. In the case of the Technologic de Monterrey, it is mentioned that this committee will be made up of “Three people from within the Technologic appointed by the Office, by the gender perspective criteria, in addition to an expert on gender issues, a representative of Disciplinary Affairs (Student Leadership and Training: LiFE; Comprehensive Wellbeing and Student Development: by of or its equivalent) and one or one of Talent and Culture. In the case of the Universidad Iberoamericana Ciudad de México-Tijuana, it is noted that the Committee is made up of two academics from IBERO, who are appointed by the academic vice-rector (and at least one must be a woman), and three externals, appointed from the rectorate (and at least two must be women). Finally, in the case of ITAM, the responsible body will be made up of a professor from each of the Academic Divisions, and a representative of the students or the administrative sector if these sectors were involved in the complaint; the selection would be in charge of the Academic Direction [19].

Despite the existence of protocols to eradicate gender-based violence in university spaces According to [20-21] 2 out of 10 women who went through these events approach the authorities to ask for help, 32.6% go to the public ministry to raise the corresponding complaint, a significant proportion of 32% resorted to the DIF and others to a lesser extent resorted to other authorities such as the police 20%, the municipal presidency 15.4% and women's institutes only 9% of the women affected by gender violence.

4. Final thoughts

Gender violence is an issue that has been debated for several years, for a long time it has been mostly reflected towards women, who represent a greater number of cases that suffer from this type of situation. Although there are a large number of types of violence that even occur every day in a large part of the population, the custom and frequency of these acts mean that those involved do not accept or realize that they are exercising or suffering some type of violence.

But it is not only the case in the home where these situations occur, but also at work, in society, and in educational institutions violence occurs, whether it is towards men or women, who have to deal with this conflict that has started today does not receive adequate attention from the authorities, because due to daily situations they prefer to ignore the cases that come to them.

This originates that groups, especially women who represent a greater percentage of the population that suffers acts of violence through movements, seek a solution from the authorities, whether governmental or institutional, to feel more secure and that the complaints that are presented are attended to carry out the corresponding sanctions by the aggressors, who, due to the lack of attention to this situation by the same authorities, continue with the aggressions.

As you have seen before, violence is not only presented physically and verbally but also psychologically, it affects the people who suffer it, thus generating even permanent damage to their person, which can generate several cases of damage to their self-esteem and security.

5. Conclusion

It includes content in study plans and programs with a gender perspective that empower students.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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